

Historical and Research Review of the Scholarly Position of Syedina Hazrat Ali (RA)

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Abstract

The fourth pious caliph of Islam Hazrat Ali Bin Abu Talib R.A is considered a remarkable personality of Islam. He accepted Islam in his early age when he was only ten and had become a very close companion of the Prophet (PBUH). He remained caliph after the Martyrdom of Hazrat Usman Ghani in 36 A.H. Hazrat Ali R.A was also great scholar. Apart from political and military affairs, Hazrat Ali has a high academic status. All the great companions of the Prophet were appreciative of his erudition. That is why people like Hazrat Ayesha, Abdullah bin Masood would not give any opinion after their opinion. He was proficient in Quran, Hadith, principles, rules and language. He had a unique position based on his high academic status. This research article highlights the status quo within his personality.

Keywords: Hazrat Ali, Islam, Madinat-ul- Ilim, Knowledge, Caliph, etc.

Introduction

Hazrat Ali was the son of Hazrat Abu Talib the uncle of the Prophet Hazrat Muhammad (PBUH). From his early childhood, Hazrat Ali (RA) lived with Prophet Hazrat Muhammad (PBUH). Hence, he was brought up in the care of the Prophet Hazrat Muhammad (PBUH). Hazrat Ali was the first among children to accept Islam. He was at that time only ten years old. He served lot for Islam and remained very close to Prophet Hazrat Muhammad (PBUH). He participated in wars as well as he was the great scholar of Islam. He was a very courageous man. That is why, he is also known as "Asadullah", meaning "the Lion of Allah. During the war of Khyber, Rasoolullah (PBUH) handed Hazrat Ali (RA) the Islamic flag and Allah granted victory to the Muslims. Hazrat Muhammad had married of his beloved daughter Hazrat Fatima to Hazrat Ali (R.A). Hazrat Hassan (R.A) and Hazrat Hussain (R.A) were the sons of Hazrat Ali (R.A). Rasoolullah (S.A.W) loved Hazrat Hassan and Hazrat Hussain very much. After the martyrdom of Hazrat Usman Hazrat Ali (R.A) became the fourth caliph of Islam. He performed his duties as a caliph for almost five years. Hazrat Ali (RA) wrote many letters and Treaties for the Holy Prophet (PBUH). He is the head of all orders of Walis. The scholarly personality is also prominent as Islam. You have the status of Sanad in the complete mastery of the Quran and Hadith, Shariah and worldly sciences and in the interpretation of issues. As a scholar he was also well versed in worldly sciences and that is why all the

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Companions used to take the solution of scientific problems to him.

Research Methodology

This dissertation is an analytical study on the basic level and its research has adopted the historical method of research and has adopted a qualitative approach which has been taken from the primary and secondary sources with the help of documentary materials. These sources include books, articles, and Newspapers, etc.

Literature Review

In historical research literature considered very important component of the research and for this research topic various documentary sources has been discussed. Hadeth, Tareekh-e-Islam, Ashra Mubashrah, Khulfa-e-Rashideen and many important books i.e Tareekh-ul-Khulfa etc.

Discussion

The Conqueror of Khyber, Haider-e-Karar, the Lion of God, the first person to convert to Islam Your path is a long list of services and sacrifices in Islam that are impossible to cover. As the son of the Holy Prophet, the advisor of the caliphs, the leader of the army, you look simple and elegant with all kinds of virtues. Apart from being as sabiqoon-ul-Awaloon, Jan Nisaran in Islam. He is also known as a scholar of Islam. You have the status of Sanad in the complete mastery of the Qur'an and Hadith, Shariah and modern sciences and in the interpretation of issues. That's why he is known as the door of knowledge Islam. He did important work by explaining the Shariah issues as well as by working on the Quran and Arabic for the first time in Arabic through his student Aswad. Nature had endowed you with such intellectual capacity in the field of knowledge that you could easily solve extremely difficult problems. That is why Abdullah Ibn Masood (may Allah be pleased with him) narrates.

إِنَّ عَلِيَّ بْنَ أَبِي تَالِبٍ عِنْدَهُ عِلْمُ الْفَاظِ وَالْبَاطِنِ¹

No doubt Hazrat Ali R.A was well aware from all kind and branches of knowledge which are visible or invisible.

أَكْبَرُ فِي أَصْحَابِ مُحَمَّدٍ صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَآلِهِ وَسَلَّمَ أَحَدًا عُلِمَ مِنْ عَلِيٍّ؟ قَالَ لَا وَاللَّهِ مَا عُلِمَ

Thus Abdul Malik Ibn Abi Sulayman says that I asked Hazrat Atta (may Allah be pleased with him). Was there any scholar among the companions of Muhammad (peace be upon him) Rizwanullah (peace be upon him) more than Ali (peace be upon him)? He said: No, by God, I do not know such a person.²

If we discuss the scholarly position of Ameer-ul-Momineen Hazrat Syedna Ali-ul-Murtada, it is not possible to cover it. Hazrat Ali (RA) converted to Islam at the age of ten and took the lead in converting children to Islam. They were the first children to convert to Islam. He was only the fourth person to convert to Islam as a child. As a child, he excelled in converting to Islam, but he also found a special place in the field of knowledge. Hazrat Ali (may Allah bless him and grant him peace) was with the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) at all times since his childhood.

He used to spend his time in the company of the Holy Prophet (PBUH) whether it was at home or traveling abroad or he had a unique place due to being with the Holy Prophet (PBUH).

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Hazrat Ali (RA) used to follow the habits of the Holy Prophet (PBUH) and follow them. Hazrat Ayesha Siddique (RA) says that Hazrat Ali (RA) was the one who knew and adopted the Sunnah more.³ Hazrat Ali (RA) was endowed with intellectual abilities and that is why the Holy Prophet (PBUH) himself repeatedly described the scholarly position of Hazrat Ali (RA) as the gateway to knowledge and wisdom. He praised the knowledge of Hazrat Ali (RA) in many places. According to the hadith, I am the city of knowledge in Madinat-ul-Alam and Ali Baba and Ali is its gate.⁴

انادار الحكيمو علي بابها⁵

Another place he said: I am the house of wisdom and Ali (may Allah be pleased with him) is its door.

Knowledge of grammar is also very important for linguistics and speech. Another achievement of Hazrat Ali (RA) is the elementary education of grammar. The reason for this is that once you heard some non-Muslim non-Muslims reciting the Qur'an in Kufa, you were very sorry to know their mistakes. So he called his student Abu al-Aswad and explained the principles of grammar. And to make the problems of the common people easier by compiling the principles of grammar. And let's make the first two or three rules for this. One of the aims of which was to save both Arabic and non-Arabic people from misreading the Holy Qur'an. These were the basic rules of grammar, thanks to which grammar has become a great knowledge today.⁶

Hazrat Ali (RA) was considered as the personal secretary of the Holy Prophet (PBUH) due to his knowledge. Most of the correspondence is assigned to you. In addition to writing revelations, he also wrote various agreements, especially with tribes and nations. Out of these agreements, you wrote the agreement made on the occasion of the peace treaty. And then he refused to cut the word Rasoolullah in it. Because you are between Quraysh and Muslims- The representative of Quraysh in Makkah objected that we do not consider Muhammad to be the Messenger of Allah. Hazrat Ali (AS) said: I cannot erase these words with my own hand (because they are based on fact). The Holy Prophet (PBUH) cut these words with his own blessed hand.⁷ Hazrat Ali, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, was considered to be very knowledgeable and a man of opinion on the basis of his scholarly position. His foresight, intellect and insight were unparalleled. Being a source of wisdom, you made big decisions. And for this reason, the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) made you the judge of Yemen or where you played a practical role in providing justice to the people.⁸

Hazrat Ali was considered more suitable than all the Companions due to his deep insight into the Quran, Sunnah, Rafqa and Ijtihad. Hazrat Umar used to say: "Hazrat Ali is the most suitable among us to decide cases." Hazrat Abdullah bin Masood said: "We used to say that Hazrat Ali is the most correct judge among the people of Madinah. It should be noted that the Holy Prophet had appointed Hazrat Ali as the judge of Yemen. He also prayed for them and taught them the basic principles of making up. The Holy Prophet had told them. "Ali! When you start quarreling between two men, don't judge by just one man's statement. Hold on to your decision until you hear the other person's statement."⁹ Hazrat Ali (RA) says that once the Prophet (PBUH) prayed for me. The Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) placed his hand on my chest and prayed: O Allaah, fill Ali's chest with knowledge, wisdom, wisdom and light.¹⁰

It is narrated on the authority of Hazrat Ali (may Allaah be pleased with him) that the

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Messenger of Allaah (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) said to me: Teach me a thousand chapters of knowledge Hazrat Ali (RA) was very proud of his knowledge and Hazrat Ali (RA) while explaining his intellectual ability says: Ask what you have to ask, then Hazrat Abu Tufail Amir bin Wathila (RA) says Ali (may Allah be pleased with him) was present in the service of Allah (may Allah bless him and grant him peace). I will definitely answer.¹¹ Similarly, Saeed ibn Musaib (may Allah be pleased with him), one of the famous books of Tabein (may Allah be pleased with him) says that there is no one among the companions of Prophet (peace be upon him) except Hazrat Ali (may Allah be pleased with him) who says: He had the highest level of knowledge.¹²

Similarly, Hazrat Ali (may Allah bless him and grant him peace) says about the verses of the Holy Quran that I know which verse has been revealed when and where and when. Ask about Kareem. Verily, I know of every verse of the Qur'an whether it is revealed in the night or in the day. Allah says (interpretation of the meaning): "By Allah, I know every verse of the Holy Quran, when and where it was revealed, and about whom it was revealed."¹³

Hazrat Abdullah bin Masood (may Allah be pleased with him) who has been given the title of Resurrection towards the scholarly position and status of Ali (may Allah be pleased with him) says that when it comes to understanding the Qur'an, it would not be wrong to say about Ali Al-Murtada that Amir-ul-Momineen Syedna Ali Allah Almighty knows that those who have knowledge of both the outward and the inward of the Holy Qur'an and they have access to their knowledge which is not available to anyone else.¹⁴

Explaining the meaning of the verses of the Holy Qur'an about the outward and the inward to explain an issue, Ahmadiyar Khan Naeemi (may Allah have mercy on him) said: The inner is the way or the outward signs, and the inner is the insistence or the outward is what the scholars have met and talked about, like the character of the Sufis who know what is known. If the Companions of Rizwan Allaah (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) knew about the fatwa of Hazrat Ali (R.A) in any matter, then the Companions would follow his fatwa. The person would tell us If Hazrat Ali (RA) has this fatwa in this matter, then we would never go beyond it.¹⁵

Most of the Companions used to turn to Hazrat Ali (RA) for solution and interpretation of problems. Similarly, Umm Al-Mu'minin Hazrat Ayesha (RA) used to send people to Hazrat Ali (RA) in some matters. Hazrat Sohaib bin Sanan (may Allah be pleased with him) asked Hazrat Ayesha (may Allah be pleased with her) about wiping on the subject. Know more than Hazrat Abdullah bin Masood (may Allah be pleased with him) says that Hazrat Ali Al-Murtada (may Allah be pleased with him) was the one who knew the knowledge of inheritance the most among the people of Madinah.¹⁶ Hazrat Ali (RA) was an expert in memorizing hadiths and the number of hadiths narrated from him is 586. Which are present in Bukhari Muslim Tirmidhi Mustadrak¹⁷

Hazrat Ali (RA) was an expert in memorizing hadiths and the number of hadiths narrated from him is 586. Which are present in Bukhari Muslim Tirmidhi Mustadrak.¹⁸ Hazrat Ali (R) Was an Expert in Memorizing Hadithas and was the number of Hadithas narrated from us. Wehich hey percent in Bukhari Muslim Termidhi Mustadrak.¹⁹

Allama Jalal-ud-Din Suyuti narrates that Abu Aswad says that one day I came to the service of Hazrat Ali (RA). I have heard that the vocabulary in your city has started to change, so I intend to make some rules within the rules of Arabic. Do not let the Arabic language fall into its

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status. We will be very kind and give you eternal life because they will always be after you. In the same way, when I returned after three days, you took out a piece of paper and put it in front of me. The one who informs and fails is the one who informs about the movement of his masmi and the letter is the one in which these two characteristics are not found. In the same way, he also formulated the letters Nasaba.²⁰

Hazrat Abu Thabit (may Allah be pleased with him), the slave of Hazrat Abu Dharr (may Allah be pleased with him) narrates that Umm Salma (may Allah be pleased with her) narrated that I heard the Messenger of Allah (may peace be upon him) saying:

على مع القرآن والقرآن مع علي، لن يتفرقا حتى يردا على نالجوض۔

Conclusion

The characteristic of Hazrat Ali, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, was that it was a system of government based on the Qur'an and Sunnah. Establishment of the Caliphate of Hazrat Ali (RA) from 656 to 661 AH, four years and eight months. Hazrat Ali, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, holds a very high position among the scholars of Sahaba. His fatwas and decisions are the jewel of Islamic knowledge Hazrat Ibn Abbas (may Allah be pleased with him) says that whenever we ask you about a problem, you always get the correct answer. There is no one who knows more about Shariah than Ali Don't get me wrong. Hazrat Ali, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, holds a very high position among the scholars of Sahaba. His fatwas and decisions are the jewel of Islamic knowledge Hazrat Ibn Abbas (may Allah be pleased with him) says that whenever we ask you about a problem, you always get the correct answer. There is no one who knows more about Shariah than Ali Don't get me wrong.

References

1. Abu Naeem, Hulyat-ul-Aoliya wa Tabqat-ul- Asfiya, Vol. I, Tarjma Urdu, 1988, P.105
2. Ibbn-e-Abi Shayba, Voll-XVII, P.123.
3. Muqadma Ibn-e-Islah, P.300
4. Ibn-e-Asakar, Tareekh Ibn-e-Asakar, 42: P.408
5. Jami'a Tarimzi, Vol-V, 3744,, P.402
6. Muhammad Ismaeel Panipati, Das Bary Log,(10 Great People), Lahore, 1965, P.127
7. Afzal, R. Tareekh-e-Islam, Lahore, 2011, P. 157
8. Muhammad Ismaeel Panipati, Das Bary Log,(10 Great People), Lahore,, 1965, P.128-129
9. Tareekh-e-Islam. P. 214.
10. Ibn-e-Asakar, P.286
11. Jami-ul-biyan-ul-Iliim-ul-F azlah, P.157.
12. Ibn-e-Abi Shaibah, 13, P.457
13. Muhammad Bin Saad, Tabqat-Ibne-Saad, Vol-II, Karachi, 1985, P.257
14. Ibn-e-Asakar, P.400
15. Tabqat-Ibne-Saad, P.258.
16. Al-Istiyab, III, P. 260.
17. Tabqat-Ibne-Saad, Vol-III, P.27.
18. Hakim, Mustarak, III, P.108.
19. Tarimzi, Kitab-ul-Manqib-e-Ali
20. Allama Jalal-u-Din Sayuti, Tareekh-ul-Khulfa, Lahore, 2008, P.214